

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SUBLINGUAL IMMUNOTHERAPY IN CHILDREN WITH RESPIRATORY ALLERGIES

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Аннотация. Сублингвальный АСИТ — единственный этиопатогенетический метод терапии респираторных аллергозов у детей — назначается при наличии четких доказательств связи между экспозицией аллергена, симптомами болезни и IgE-зависимым механизмом, имеет продолжительную эффективность и может предотвращать прогрессирование аллергических болезней: уменьшает вероятность формирования бронхиальной астмы у больных аллергическим ринитом и конъюнктивитом и расширения спектра сенсибилизации.

Ключевые слова: респираторный аллергоз, сублингвальная иммуно терапия, дети, аллергический ринит, бронхиальная астма.

Abstract. Sublingual ASIT, the only etiopathogenetic method of therapy for respiratory allergies in children, is prescribed when there is clear evidence of a link between allergen exposure, disease symptoms and IgE-dependent mechanism, has long-lasting efficacy and can prevent the progression of allergic diseases: it reduces the likelihood of bronchial asthma formation in patients with allergic rhinitis and conjunctivitis and expands the spectrum of sensitization.

Keywords: respiratory allergosis, sublingual immunotherapy, children, allergic rhinitis, bronchial asthma.

Annotatsiya. Sublingual ASIT bolalarda nafas olish allergiyasini davolashning yagona etiopatogenetik usuli bo'lib, agar allergen ta'siri, kasallik belgilari va IgE ga bog'liq mexanizm o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikning aniq dalillari mavjud bo'lsa, buyuriladi, uzoq muddatli samaradorlikka ega va allergik kasalliklarning rivojlanishini oldini oladi: allergik rinit va kon'yunktivit bilan og'rigan bemorlarda bronxial astma paydo bo'lish ehtimolini kamaytiradi va sensibilizatsiya spektrini kengaytiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: respirator allergozlar, sublingual immunoterapiya, bolalar, allergik rinit, bronxial astma.

Topicality

Allergic diseases belong to the most common in children, and in recent years there has been a significant increase in the frequency and more severe course of allergic diseases, in connection with which they are considered in modern society as a major medical and social problem. According to different authors, the frequency of allergic diseases varies widely, depending on the diagnostic criteria used and the methods of epidemiologic research.

Respiratory allergic diseases - bronchial asthma (BA) and allergic rhinitis (AR) - are characterized by a variable course. Progression of the disease is often observed over the years: the frequency and severity of exacerbations and the need for pharmacopreparations necessary to maintain disease control increase [1,2,4,5].

Allergic diseases belong to the most common diseases in children, and in recent years there has been a significant increase in the frequency and more severe course of allergic diseases, therefore they are considered in modern society as a major medical and social problem. The frequency of allergic diseases, according to different authors, varies widely, depending on the

diagnostic criteria used and the methods of epidemiologic research. Thus, the prevalence of bronchial asthma according to domestic and foreign authors ranges from 0.2% to 8.1%. According to generalized data of ISAAC (International Study of Asthma and Allergies in Childhood), the frequency of BA symptoms ranges from 1.0 to 30.8%. Allergic rhinitis and pollinosis account for 0.2-20% in different regions, while atopic dermatitis and eczema account for 1.6-4.2% [3,5,1-0].

In recent years, alternative routes of allergen administration, especially sublingual or sublingual (SLIT), have attracted increasing interest among allergists and pediatricians. The allergen is administered as drops or easily dissolvable tablets under the tongue. This non-invasive method is more easily accepted by the child and parents [6,9,11].

ASIT (Allergen Specific Immuno Therapy) is the only method to reduce the global incidence of allergy, capable of changing the pathophysiological mechanisms of atopic diseases, halting the formation of more severe forms, as well as preventing the development of polysensitization, changing the course of the disease, improving the patient's quality of life and avoiding long-term treatment costs.

In recent years, there has been a steady increase in allergies worldwide, especially among children, and treatment costs are rising. Allergen-specific immunotherapy is the only treatment method that can change the nature of the body's response to the allergen and thus influence the course of the disease. Its prophylactic effect is associated with a reduction in the risk of increased sensitization or worsening of existing clinical manifestations.

The advent of sublingual therapeutic allergens (sublingual ASIT) has opened a new era in the use of ASIT, which is characterized by a high safety profile, efficacy and greater adherence to treatment. The main advantage of sublingual immunotherapy is high safety and absence of systemic reactions to this method of allergen administration, as well as noninvasiveness, accessibility and simplicity of execution, possibility of administration in children from 5 years of age, reduction in the number of adverse reactions and exacerbations of the underlying disease, high compliance with parents, positive attitude of children to therapy [7,8,9,10].

Materials and methods.

The assessment of ASIT efficacy was carried out according to the recommendations of the European Association of Allergists and Clinical Immunologists to determine the average score of nasal and conjunctival symptoms severity (on a 10-point scale) and the need for drug therapy to relieve symptoms. In addition, during the season of pollination of causative plants before and after ASIT, all patients answered the questions of a special Rhinoconjunctivitis Quality of Life Questionnaire (RQLQ) developed for patients with allergic rhinoconjunctivitis. The questionnaire includes a total of 28 questions and is divided into 7 main groups. The questions are focused on the assessment of daily activity, activity of rhinoconjunctivitis symptoms manifestations, sleep, emotional and practical difficulties in the season of pollination of causative plants. Assessment is made on a 7-point scale from 0 to 6, where 0 - complete absence of symptoms and discomfort, 6 - sharply pronounced disturbances of physical and psycho-emotional state.

Respiratory allergies - lesions of the nose and sinuses, larynx, trachea, bronchi and lungs. The basis of the lesion is immunologic, allergic mechanisms. Immunologic conflict and its nature depends on allergenic exposure and immune response of the organism, determined by genetic factors, hormonal influence. The following clinical symptoms and quality of life of patients were evaluated in the examined children in the main group: nasal congestion and itching in 99.4%, nasal discharge, sneezing 94.9%, smell disturbance 88.4%;, itching of the palate and

ears 79.9%, itching and redness of the eyes 76.8%, lacrimation 75.8%, photophobia 73.7%, eyelid edema 72.2% and narrowing of the eye slit, feeling of "sand in the eyes" in 71.3%. Asthma symptoms: dyspnea, feeling of stuffiness and heaviness in the chest, coughing, wheezing, wheezing attacks. Decreased quality of life: limitation of being outdoors, poor sleep, decreased performance due to symptoms.

According to the above scale, patients rated their condition at the time of examination from 1 to 10 on a scale of 1 to 10 before ASIT, after 1 year of treatment, and after 3 years of treatment.

The most commonly considered criteria for the clinical efficacy of ASIT is the assessment of symptom severity over a specific period of time related to pollen exposure. The average symptom score for allergic rhinoconjunctivitis is based on daily assessment of rhinitis (sneezing, nasal itching, nasal discharge, nasal congestion) and conjunctivitis (itchy eyes, redness and lacrimation) symptoms on a 10-point scale.

ASIT reduces the severity of symptoms and also reduces the need for medications. Assessment of the need for medication (MS) is a mandatory criterion for the clinical efficacy of ASIT. The importance of studying the quality of life of patients with allergic diseases is well known. In addition to clinical criteria (assessment of symptom severity and need for medication, assessment of quality of life), objective data obtained by spirometry, allergen provocation tests, exposure chambers, anterior active rhinomanometry, acoustic rhinomanometry, or peak nasal inspiratory flow measurements are used to assess the efficacy of ASIT.

For evaluation, a general quality of life (QOL) index and an index for each of the selected groups are calculated. In addition to assessing the activity of rhinoconjunctivitis symptoms, this questionnaire takes into account the need for drug therapy: symptomatic (bronchodilators, decongestants), basal (topical glucocorticosteroids, antileukotriene drugs, cromoglycates), antihistamines. The questionnaire is filled out by the patient after the course of ASIT. It consists of 20 questions, the assessment is made on a 6-point scale from 0 to 5, where 0 - maximum manifestations, 5 - complete absence of symptoms and the need for drug therapy

Already in the first season of pollination after SLIT all patients noted a decrease in the severity of nasal and conjunctival symptoms and a decrease in the need for medication to relieve symptoms. After SLIT, there was an improvement in the quality of life indicators in all 7 domains reflecting the main aspects of normal human activity: activity limitation, sleep, nasal and conjunctival symptoms, general symptoms, practical problems, and emotional background. The index of patients' QOL before ASIT averaged 1.6 ± 0.5 , after SLIT - 0.6 ± 0.35 .

When ASIT with household allergens (house dust mites, spores of mold fungi) was performed by sublingual method, excellent and good effect was observed in 83.3% of children. In sublingual ASIT, the number of children with concomitant AD was higher than with AR.

Treatment efficacy increased depending on the duration of therapy. The influence of patients' age on treatment efficacy was noted. The earlier ASIT was started, the more powerful was the effect of therapy [5,8,9].

Results and discussions.

The efficacy and safety of ASIT in respiratory allergic diseases in the examined children were studied. After ASIT, the clinical symptomatology of children improved, and the need for both baseline and emergency drugs decreased. The index of QOL of patients after ASIT was 0.6 ± 0.35 ($p < 0.05$).

When ASIT was performed in children aged 4-7 years, a positive effect was observed in 84.2% of children, in children aged 7- 12 years - 73.6%, in children aged 12-18 years - 71.9%

($p < 0.05$). At multivalent sensitization positive effect was observed in 88,2 % of patients, at polyvalent in 76,7 % ($p < 0,05$) of cases.

The immunomodulatory effect of ASIT in children with AR and AD was noted in the course of treatment. In addition to the positive effect on the course of allergic diseases, the frequency of acute respiratory diseases decreased in 38.7% of patients, the number of absences due to illness in preschool institutions and schools decreased, and the quality of life improved.

Thus, ASIT is an effective method of treatment of atopic diseases, which is based on the induction of tolerance to allergens. The greatest effectiveness of SLIT is achieved in the treatment of respiratory allergies. Pollinosis (allergy to plant pollen) is one of the most frequent allergic diseases. The most frequent manifestations of pollinosis are allergic rhinitis, allergic conjunctivitis, and bronchial asthma.

It is a generally recognized fact that the greatest effect of ASIT is achieved at the earliest start of treatment from the debut of the disease. Properly performed ASIT changes the natural course of allergic disease and prevents the formation of bronchial asthma. As mentioned above, in recent years, SLIT has become the most frequently used technique in the treatment of children. First of all, this is due to the high safety profile of such treatment - low reactogenicity of SLIT, low probability of systemic reactions. An important factor is the greater compliance of patients: there is no need for frequent visits to the doctor, there is no resistance to treatment (young children are unable to realize the need for injections, for them it is stressful, accompanied by crying and active resistance).

Sublingual ASIT compared to the parenteral method has a number of advantages: simplicity and painlessness of administration, absence of severe systemic reactions, the possibility of self-administration of the allergy vaccine at home, saving the patient's time, and high adherence to treatment.

Thus, SLASIT, the only etiopathogenetic method of therapy for respiratory allergies in children, is prescribed when there is clear evidence of a link between allergen exposure, disease symptoms, and an IgE-dependent mechanism. ASIT induces clinical and immunological tolerance, has long-lasting efficacy and can prevent the progression of allergic diseases: it reduces the likelihood of bronchial asthma formation in patients with allergic rhinitis and conjunctivitis and expands the spectrum of sensitization.

Allergen specific immunotherapy should be performed by a specialist allergologist-immunologist. The duration of therapy, as a rule, is 3-5 years. Selection of the drug and routes of administration are carried out by a specialist individually.

Sublingual ASIT is more preferable for children: it is painless, convenient from the point of view of the route of administration and has a more favorable safety profile compared to the subcutaneous method. Premedication with second-generation antihistamines or antileukotriene receptor antagonists can reduce the incidence and severity of adverse events.

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